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Title: Data Management Plan

Abstract: This document is the initial version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the SafeWax project. The aim of the DMP is to provide an analysis of the main components of the data management policy that has been used throughout the project. This deliverable will also support the data management life cycle for all data that will be collected, processed or generated by the project.

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Glossary:

Abbreviation	Explanation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DX.X	Deliverable X.X
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
WP	Work package

Disclosure Statement

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Executive Summary

This deliverable will comprise an initial Data Management Plan (DMP) of the SafeWax project which aligns with the Horizon Europe DMP template¹, that was designed by the European Commission (EC) to be applied to Horizon Europe projects which produce, collect or process research data. This DMP document includes information regarding:

- How the research data will be handled during & after the end of the project
- What types of data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- Which methodology & standards will be applied
- Whether data will be shared/made open access
- How data will be curated & preserved (including after the end of the project).

A practical approach to the data management life cycle will be handled by the Consortium following the FAIR Data principles in Horizon Europe initiative² as a general guideline.

Given the early stages of SafeWax development and implementation, the current deliverable document is a first version of the DMP. Therefore, it will be continuously updated throughout the duration of the SafeWax project.

¹ Horizon Europe template: Data Management Plan v.1 from 05 May 2021

² Horizon Europe template: Data Management Plan v.1 from 05 May 2021

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1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the document

SafeWax DMP was designed with the primary goal of facilitating comprehensive data lifecycle management. This encompasses all forms of data generated, gathered, and manipulated within the scope of the Horizon Europe project. This deliverable's core objective revolves around pinpointing optimal methodologies and precise benchmarks that pertain to the project's data. An additional aim is to evaluate their appropriateness for seamless sharing and subsequent utilization, aligning with established official protocols.

Presently, the SafeWax consortium is unwavering in its dedication to the European Commission's overarching objective of enhancing the discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of research data. This commitment is in full alignment with the FAIR principles, which advocate for data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

1.2. Scope of the document

The content of the document adheres to the DMP template established by the European Commission (EC) for FAIR Data Management within the Horizon Europe initiative. It encompasses the subsequent details:

- **Guiding Principles and Strategy of DMP:** The document outlines the fundamental principles and the strategic methodology underpinning the DMP.
- **SafeWax Data Classification:** This section provides a comprehensive description of the various types of data unique to the SafeWax project.
- **Introduction to FAIR Data:** A clear introduction is provided to elucidate the concept of FAIR Data, highlighting its significance in the context of the project.
- **Allocation of Resources:** The document expounds upon the allocation of resources dedicated to the efficient management of data within the project's scope.
- **Data Security Measures:** This section is dedicated to the various measures and protocols implemented to ensure the security of the project's data.
- **Ethical Considerations:** The document also addresses the ethical facets associated with the management of data, ensuring compliance

with ethical standards and regulations.

By adhering to the outlined structure, the document comprehensively covers essential aspects in line with the DMP Horizon Europe template guidelines for FAIR Data Management within the Horizon Europe framework.

1.3. DMP guiding principles and strategy

The imperative for all projects funded under Horizon Europe is to ensure widespread dissemination of information. Furthermore, the SafeWax project is committed to providing unrestricted access to all generated project data, unless it runs counter to the legitimate interests of the consortium.

In light of this, the primary objective of the DMP is to significantly contribute to the accessibility and comprehensibility of data produced throughout the project's execution. This effort is undertaken to align with the Guidelines of the DMP Horizon Europe concept.

The SafeWax DMP is executed within the framework of Work Package 6, which is dedicated to project coordination and management. This strategy underscores the consortium's overarching plan to effectively leverage research outcomes and aligns with the Open Access principles upheld by the EC.

Guided by these considerations, the core principles guiding the SafeWax project are outlined below:

- The DMP has been accurately prepared in adherence to the template provided by the DMP Template in Horizon Europe.³
- The DMP holds the status of an official project Deliverable (D6.2), with a scheduled submission in month 6. This initial version of the DMP will undergo iterative refinement throughout the project's execution based on evolving research activities and feedback received from European Commission (EC) representatives and other crucial project stakeholders.
- The DMP operates under the purview of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 and the Council of 27 April 2016, known as the General Data Protection

³ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

Regulation (GDPR), along with other relevant legal frameworks governing data protection.

- Types of data, storage, confidentiality, ownership, intellectual property management, and access protocols; procedures governing data collection, storage, access, sharing policies, security measures, retention, and eventual data destruction will align with established EU standards, as detailed in both the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

2.Data Summary

The DMP strategy employed by the SafeWax project is centered on adhering to the principles of FAIR Data Management Protocols (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

Each dataset originating from the project will undergo an evaluation process where the content owners will determine whether it falls into one of three categories: open, embargoed, or restricted. Overseeing this process, the project coordinator will ensure a consistent and unified approach to decision-making.

A preliminary list of datasets types expected to be produced throughout the project includes the following:

- Experimental and observational data collected using measurement devices and analytical instruments;
- Data derived from the analysis of the the experimental data or literature data;
- Methodologies, protocols, and workflows, standard operating procedures, multimedia and physical documents (reports, spreadsheets, presentations) to present SafeWax results data;
- Survey and interview data, obtained from SafeWax partners and potential stakeholders and focus groups;
- Images;
- Videos.

The main formats of the data generated/collected will include:

- Reports, spreadsheets, presentations - Microsoft Office formats, .pdf
- Observed data (experimental) - original format, .csv, .mpr, .mps, .txt, .fasta, .fastq;
- Images – .jpg, .gif, .tiff, .png;
- Audio – .mp3;
- Videos – .mpg, .avi, .mp4;

All generated datasets, regardless of their categorization, will be stored within the databases of each beneficiary. Moreover, datasets categorized as open or embargoed will be shared with the public, with embargoed data becoming accessible once the specified period has lapsed. This sharing will occur through both the ZENODO project profile.

ZENODO stands as an open-access repository that welcomes a wide array of data formats, as recommended by the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE).

Datasets of particular significance for dissemination purposes will be featured on the project website and disseminated through appropriate social media channels.

Within the array of project outputs—including datasets, deliverables, and related documentation—categories have been designated as "ORDP" (Open Research Data Policy). Consequently, these outputs will inherently be designated as "Open Access," meaning they will be made available for public sharing at no cost. These categories encompass:

- Project deliverables explicitly labeled as public within the Grant Agreement (following formal approval by EC services);
- Articles set to be published in Open Access scientific journals (following the acceptance for publication);
- Conference and Workshop abstracts/articles.

In Annex 1 of this deliverable, the consortium members have outlined the potential data types that can arise per work package. Although not exhaustive, this list may expand as the project advances. Maintaining the table's contents and ensuring its currency will be the responsibility of the project coordinator, utilizing a centralized register accessible upon request. Each project dataset and document will be assigned a status of "open," "embargoed," or "restricted."

3. FAIR Data

In the year 2016, the publication of the '[FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship](#)' within Scientific Data⁴ established a set of guidelines aimed at enhancing the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets.

Central to these principles is the notion of machine-actionability—a concept reflecting the capability of computational systems to independently locate, access, interoperate, and reuse data with minimal to no human intervention. This emphasis on automation acknowledges the escalating reliance on computational tools to manage data. Such reliance has emerged in response to the exponential surge in data volume, the growing intricacy of data, and the accelerated pace at which data is generated.

In accordance with these enduring principles, SafeWax project aligns its data management strategy. The FAIR principles serve as a foundational framework to effectively coordinate the organization and administration of research and development data arising from the project.

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The primary step in effectively (re)utilizing data involves their discovery. Both metadata and data should be easily acquired by both human researchers and computational systems. Machine-readable metadata play a pivotal role in enabling automated finding of datasets and services, constituting a fundamental element in generating FAIR data.

Metadata essentially represent information about the research data itself. Their presence enables fellow researchers to efficiently search for datasets within online repositories, rendering them indispensable for ensuring the reusability of these datasets. By incorporating comprehensive and detailed metadata, researchers are empowered to assess whether a dataset holds relevance and utility for their own investigations.

Within the scope of SafeWax's activities, metadata, encompassing

⁴ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016).

information like data type and location, will be uploaded in a standardized format. Notably, this metadata will be maintained separately from the original raw research data. As outlined in the project's Grant Agreement (Article 17.4, Annex 5), the bibliographic metadata for SafeWax will encompass the following details:

- The terms "European Union (EU)" and "Horizon Europe"
- The name of the action, its acronym, and grant number
- Publication date, including the duration of any embargo period if applicable
- A persistent identifier

Safeweax's open data will be consolidated within the ZENODO online research data repository (see Section 2 above). This repository aligns its structure, functions, and administration with the principles of FAIR data. ZENODO serves as a platform allowing researchers to deposit both publications and data, providing mechanisms to link them through persistent identifiers and data citations. Its design aims to facilitate the finding, access, re-use, and interoperability of datasets, all of which constitute fundamental principles that Horizon Europe projects are mandated to uphold.

Operated by CERN, ZENODO offers a range of capabilities, enabling researchers, scientists, EU projects, and institutions to perform the following actions:

- Share research outcomes in diverse formats such as text, spreadsheets, audio, video, and images across all scientific domains.
- Present research results, achieving recognition by rendering research outcomes citable and integrating them into established reporting structures for funding agencies like the European Commission.
- Conveniently access and reuse shared research results.
- Integrate research outputs with the OpenAIRE portal.

Additionally, ZENODO facilitates straightforward and advanced search queries through keywords, enhancing the discoverability of content. To streamline searches, the SafeWax consortium will implement a straightforward naming convention. Files and folders will be structured and versioned as follows: SafeWax_ID_YYYYMMDD_Vzz, wherein ID represents a distinctive identifier, YYYYMMDD signifies the creation date, and Vzz denotes the version number, incrementing with each revision.

3.2. Making data accessible

In order to maximize the widespread impact of SafeWax's research data, the project outcomes will be made available freely, both within and beyond the consortium, unless it contradicts the legitimate interests of the partners involved.

Chosen data and results will be disseminated to the scientific community and various stakeholders through such as presentations at conferences as well as workshops. Additionally, open access data repositories will be utilized for distribution. As previously highlighted, the SafeWax consortium is firmly committed to adhering to FAIR principles whenever possible. In terms of scientific publications, preference will be given to esteemed high-ranking journals within the relevant disciplines.

With this in consideration, Green Open Access is the preferred strategy for disseminating project findings. However, certain editorial guidelines in renowned journals like Nature might necessitate the utilization of Gold Access in specific instances. The necessary fees related to publishing "Gold" papers have already been accounted for in the project budget. The distribution of these costs among multiple authors will be determined on a case-by-case basis.

Both Green and Gold manuscripts will be freely accessible via the dedicated ZENODO project site (as detailed in Section 2). Additionally, these manuscripts will be accurately categorized and preserved within the institutional repositories of TECH and UniBO. This preservation will adhere to the established policies of these academic partners and meet the requirements set forth by journal editors.

In order to safeguard the project's intellectual property rights, the utilization of Creative Commons licenses (such CC BY, CC BY-SA and CC0) will be implemented in specific situations. Should data not be classified as free, potential users will need to establish contact with the project's IPR (Intellectual Property Rights) team or the data owner to gain access. When deemed necessary, appropriate IPR procedures such as non-disclosure agreements will be applied to ensure confidentiality and protection of project knowledge.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Enabling data interoperability is pivotal for advancing cross-cutting, collaborative, and interdisciplinary research activities. This often entails integrating data with other datasets. To achieve this, data must interoperate with applications or workflows designed for analysis, storage, and processing.

Within the context of the SafeWax project:

- Metadata will be encoded using a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language that facilitates knowledge representation.
- Metadata will adopt a vocabulary that aligns with the principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR).
- Metadata will incorporate well-defined references to other pertinent (meta)data.

These overarching principles will be put into practice by adhering to OpenAIRE guidelines for online interoperability. This includes following OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories, OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives, and OpenAIRE Guidelines for CRIS (Current Research Information Systems) Managers based on CERIF-XML⁵.

As the project advances and accumulates data, more comprehensive and detailed strategies for achieving data interoperability will be outlined in subsequent iterations of the DMP. These adaptations will be informed by the evolving nature of the generated data, guaranteeing a customized strategy that effectively promotes interoperability.

3.4. Making data re-use

The safeguarding of dataset ownership will involve the use of Creative Commons Licensing⁶ when deemed necessary. However, there might be instances where an embargo period is imposed, particularly if the data (or portions thereof) are employed in articles published in both "Green" open access and "Gold" journals.

⁵ <https://openaire-guidelines-for-literature-repository-managers.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁶ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>

The EC recommends a maximum embargo period of 6 months, and as such, project participants will strive to adhere to this guideline whenever feasible.

For datasets lodged within a public data repository like the ZENODO project site, access to free data will be unrestricted in terms of time, but usage might be subject to specific limitations. These restrictions could encompass:

- The "embargo" period as dictated by the journal's publication policy (whether it follows Green Open Access or Gold journals).
- A selection or all of the ensuing restrictions, which may be enacted via Creative Commons licensing of the dataset:
 - *Attribution*. This entails that users of the dataset are required to provide appropriate credit, include a link to the license, and indicate any modifications made.
 - *NonCommercial*. This provision bars others from utilizing the dataset for commercial purposes unless expressly agreed upon with the data owners in advance.
 - *ShareAlike*. This requirement mandates that others must apply the same license as the original to any derivative works built upon the original dataset.

These aspects will undergo more comprehensive elaboration in future iterations of the DMP as the project's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) strategy becomes more refined.

4. Allocation of Resources

Effectively managing data acquired during the SafeWax project entails a significant allocation of resources. Partners will bear these associated costs by utilizing the EC-grant as well as their own resources. As a general rule, each partner assumes responsibility for the data they generate.

In a simplified breakdown, the costs for achieving FAIR data include:

- Archiving data on platforms like ZENODO and other online databases. Data items will be retained for the lifetime of the ZENODO platform and will be backed up every 12 h.
- Obtaining copyright licenses with Creative Commons (typically free of direct charges).

The responsibility of supervising the Data Management of research data falls on the Project Coordinator, who acts on behalf of the SafeWax General Assembly. Such follow-up will consistently align with the guidelines established by the Data Protection Officers (DPOs) appointed by the partners.

It's important to note that costs associated with providing Open Access to research data within the scope of Horizon Europe are eligible for reimbursement, contingent upon the conditions outlined in the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement. Project beneficiaries hold the responsibility for initiating applications for reimbursement for costs linked to making data accessible to parties beyond the consortium.

5. Data Security

Addressing the global challenge of safeguarding confidential and restricted data is a primary concern for numerous research and development organizations in their day-to-day operations. The intrinsic value of SafeWax's data, coupled with the potential business impact that successful outcomes could bring, emphasizes the importance of data security. Such security is not only crucial for the consortium and the European Commission, but also for the broader European society.

With this paramount consideration, the following guidelines will be implemented to ensure the confidentiality, availability, and integrity of SafeWax's data:

- Data will be deposited, stored and backed up on a trusted repository Zenodo
- Data encryption will be employed when deemed necessary by participating researchers.
- Sensitive data will be stored in a cloud storage service such as Microsoft 365 OneDrive, where it is the coordinator's responsibility to ensure that the data are protected from unauthorized access and possible compromise, such as through hacking.
- Recovery of the sensitive the data, their functionality, integrity, and availability that were affected by the security incident will be performed via tools such as backup systems, data recovery software, encryption tools, and patch management to recover and secure the SafeWax data and applications.
- The use of USB flash drives will be restricted.
- Files will be systematically labeled and organized to maintain coherence in the final dataset.
- Security guidelines provided by the respective partners' IT departments will be followed.
- Backup will be ensured for the duration of the project by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative

More detailed information regarding specific security measures designed to impede and mitigate cyberattacks are categorized as confidential. The consortium will adhere to a security approach commonly referred to as "security through obscurity"⁷.

6. Ethical Aspects

All innovative and research activities conducted within the SafeWax project will adhere to universally recognized and collectively established high scientific standards encompassing ethics, integrity, and reproducibility. Researchers will uphold and advocate for these ethical tenets in research, including integrity, transparency, honesty, and respect for Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity will be embraced as a guiding framework.

The SafeWax consortium is committed to absolute transparency concerning the tools and methodologies employed throughout the project.

⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Security_through_obscurity

7. Conclusions

Presented as an initial project deliverable, this version of the DMP outlines the fundamental principles and guidelines governing data management within SafeWax.

As a dynamic document, the DMP will continue to evolve over the course of the project's duration. Subsequent revisions to the DMP will encompass an extensive data inventory. This inventory will offer comprehensive insights into the specific data being generated and collected, providing detailed descriptions and outlining the methods through which external stakeholders can access this information.

Annex 1: Data Inventory Plan

WP5 & WP6 (Business Development and Management)						
Type of data generated	Origin	Data Volume	Data Purpose	Format	Openly accessible	Comments / description
Project deliverables and reports	Inputs from all the partners generated by a WP leader	Those indicated in the GA	EC reporting obligations	.rtf & .pdf	Y	Deliverables and reports designated as "Public" will be made available through publication on Zenodo portal. Embargoed or closed data will be deposited onto institutional repositories.
Images	Inputs from partners generated by WP leader	<50 GB	EC reporting obligations	.jpg, .TIFF, .png, .pdf	Y	Figures that have not been classified as confidential or submitted for publication may potentially be disclosed.
Other	Inputs from partners generated by WP leader	NA	EC reporting obligations	.pdf, .rtf, other	N	Documentation requested by the EC services to clarify some doubts

WP5 (Regulatory activities)						
Type of data generated	Origin	Data Volume	Data Purpose	Format	Openly accessible	Comments / description
Project deliverables and study reports	Inputs from all the partners, generated by a WP leader	Those indicated in the GA	EC reporting obligations	.rtf & .pdf	Y	Deliverables and reports designated as "Public" will be made available through publication on Zenodo portal. Embargoed or closed data will be deposited onto institutional repositories.
Hazard Assessment	Personal research data	<20 units, 10 GB	EC reporting obligations	.pdf, .rtf, other	Y	Reports that have not been classified as confidential or submitted for publication may potentially be disclosed.
Literature search report	Personal research data	<10 units, 5GB	EC reporting obligations	.pdf, .rtf, other	N	Reports that have not been classified as confidential or submitted for publication may potentially be disclosed.
QSAR screening	Personal research data	<10 units, 5 GB	EC reporting obligations	.pdf, .rtf, other	N	Documentation requested by the EC services
Regulatory assessments	Personal research data	<10 units, 5GB	EC reporting obligations	.pdf, .rtf, other	N	Documentation requested by the EC services

WP6 (Dissemination & Exploitation)						
Type of data generated	Origin	Data Volume	Data Purpose	Format	Openly accessible	Comments / description
Project deliverables and reports	Contributions provided by partners and generated by the WP leader	Those indicated in the GA	EC reporting obligations	.rtf & .pdf	Y	Deliverables and reports will be made available through publication Zenodo portal. Embargoed or closed data will be deposited onto institutional repositories.
Images	Contributions provided by partners and generated by the WP leader	<500 units, 10GB	EC reporting obligations	.jpg, .TIFF, .png, .pdf	Y	Public images used for communication and dissemination activities
Conference / workshops articles and abstracts	Contributions provided by partners and generated by the WP leader	<50 units, 10GB	EC reporting obligations	.rtf & .pdf	Y	Any information that is not marked as confidential or submitted for publication may potentially be disclosed. Papers under embargo will be managed in accordance with the procedures outlined in the
Other	Contributions provided by partners and generated by the WP leader	NA	EC reporting obligations	.pdf, .rtf, .avi, .mp4, other	Y	Any supplementary actions and documents arising from workshops, training sessions, short-term missions, and strategies for exploitation

Technical WPs (WP1 – WP4)						
Type of data generated	Origin	Data Volume	Data Purpose	Format	Openly accessible	Comments / description
Project deliverables and study reports (all WPs)	Contributions provided by partners and generated by the WP leader	Those indicated in the GA	EC reporting obligations	.rtf & .pdf	Y	Deliverables and reports designated as "Public" will be made available through publication on Zenodo portal. Embargoed or closed data will be deposited onto institutional repositories.
X-Ray diffraction raw data (WP1, WP2)	PhD student	< 500 units, 10GB	Internal documentation, data sharing	.dat, .csv	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
X-Ray diffraction results (WP1, WP2)	PhD student	< 500 units, 10GB	Internal documentation, data sharing	.csv, .pdf, .tif	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
Crystallographic information files (cif files) (WP1, WP2, WP3)	Laboratories involved	< 100 units, 10GB	Internal documentation, data sharing	.cif	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
Confocal microscopy analysis files (WP1, 2, 3)	PhD student	< 500 units, 10GB	Documentation of functioning processes	.txt & .pdf	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
Confocal microscopy images files (WP1, 2, 3)	Master students and PhD students	< 100 units, 1GB	Performance characterization and documentation	jpeg, png, etc	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
Experimental logs and protocols (WP1)	Master students, Phd students and other PIs - Personal research data	< 200 units, 10GB	Internal documentation, data sharing	.rtf, .csv & .pdf	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
QCM-D datasets	Phd students, researchers, and other PIs - Personal research data	< 100 units, 5GB	Internal documentation, data sharing	.txt, .csv	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo

AFM, SEM, optical microscope images (WP3)	Laboratories involved	< 500 units, 10GB	Performance characterization and documentation	.jpeg, .png, etc	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
Experimental logs and protocols (WP2)	Phd students, researchers, and other PIs - Personal research data	< 200 units, 15GB	Internal documentation, data sharing	.csv, .rtf & .pdf	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
Wetting properties results (WP1-WP3)	Phd students, researchers and other PIs - Personal research data	< 500 units, 10GB	Internal documentation, data sharing	.csv, .png, .pdf	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
Experimental trials results (WP2 & WP3)	Phd students and other PIs - Personal research data	< 200 units, 10GB	Internal documentation, data sharing	.mph, .dat, .pdf	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
AFM, SEM, optical microscope & contact angle images (WP3)	Laboratories involved	< 100 units, 10GB	Performance characterisation and documentation	.jpeg, .png, etc	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
Experimental data sets (WP1, WP2, WP3)	Researcher, Phd students and other PIs - Personal research data	< 200 units, 10GB	Internal documentation, data sharing	.csv., .rtf & .pdf	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
Experimental logs and protocols (WP3)	Personal research data	< 100 units, 10Mb	Internal documentation, data sharing	.csv, .rtf & .pdf	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
QCM-D data analysis files	Post docs, Phd students	< 100 units, 5GB	Internal documentation, data sharing	.rtf & .pdf	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
Experimental logs of the experimental trials in vineyards (WP4)	Personal research data	< 50 units, 2GB	Internal documentation, data sharing	.csv., rtf & .pdf	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo

DSC and TGA data (WP1, WP2)	Post docs, Phd students	< 50 units, 2GB	Internal documentation, data sharing	.csv., spreadsheets	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo
Protocols of the application of SafeWax onto grape leaves (WP2)	Personal research data	< 100 units, 100MB	Internal documentation, data sharing	.csv, .rtf & .pdf	Y	At request - Deposited at Zenodo

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Confocal laser scanning microscopy images (WP1)	Post docs, Phd students and other PIs - Personal research data	Unknown	Internal documentation, data sharing	png, pdf	Y	At request - Announced at Zenodo - Ethical scrutiny needed
Esty (WP1)	Postdoc, Technician, students	Unknown	Data sets internal documentation	TIFF, JPEG	Y	Those reports labelled as Public will be published in the project website and Zenodo
Esty (WP2)	Postdoc, Technician, students	Unknown	Internal documentation, data sharing	doc, pdf	Y	At request - Announced at Zenodo - Ethical scrutiny needed
Esty (WP3)	Postdoc, Technician, students	Unknown	Internal documentation, data sharing	doc, pdf, Tiff, jpeg	Y	At request except those classified as confidential - Announced at Zenodo - Ethical scrutiny needed